

SUSAAN project aims to develop antiviral and antimicrobial surfaces including development of fast active response and durable surfaces, considering ease of use, low toxicity and health issues and finally targeting a global sustainability concept, understood as environmental, economic and social sustainability for the required product and application.

APPROACH & METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVES

- Developing a range of improved Active Nano Materials (ANMs) safely-tailored to the applications.
- Increasing fast performance and durability of the AM/AV coatings on high-traffic non-porous surfaces.
- Increasing sustainability and stability of the AM/AV coatings on textiles.
- Validating the scalability of the products and the pathways for commercialization.

WORK PLAN

- WP1** Specific definition of requirements
- WP2** Development and production of active nanomaterials
- WP3** Development and production of nanocoatings
- WP4** Application and testing on final products
- WP5** Toxicity, regulatory and sustainability assessment
- WP6** Dissemination, communication, and exploitation
- WP7** Project management

IMPACT

- Scientific** : New sustainable-by-design antimicrobial and antiviral coating with enhanced functionalities (durability, efficiency, low toxicity).
- Environmental** : Integrated life cycle sustainability assessment (ILCSA) including LCA, LCC and SLCA will provide a practical approach to integrate and harmonize a parallel assessment of individual sustainability aspects by introducing common definitions, settings and system models.
- Economic** : In the short term it is estimated that SUSAAN coatings are implemented in 30 companies, and afterwards this figure could be multiplied by 10 in the long term. This will impact on 95% of SMEs and on a sector that employs approximately 1.2 million people and 3.6 million indirectly.
- Social** : The transition to sustainable chemicals will also be mindful of socio-economic consequences including employment impacts on specific regions, in three main market sectors through end users and workers.

OUR PARTNERS

